

UNCERTAINTY REDUCTION FOR PARAMETERS OF A SEAWATER INTRUSION MODEL USING MARKOV CHAIN MONTE CARLO

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ABSTRACT

The Milrow underground nuclear test was one of three tests that were conducted on Amchitka Island, Alaska. A stochastic groundwater flow and contaminant transport model was created for the site which propagated uncertainty in input parameters through flow and transport simulations to yield an output with a wide range of uncertainty. Data pertaining to the location of the freshwater lens, derived from recent geophysical surveys on the island (Unsworth et al., 2005) provide a means for parameter uncertainty reduction. These data are used for conditioning the seawater intrusion model parameters of the Milrow site for the purpose of uncertainty reduction using a Markov Chain Monte Carlo approach. The geophysical data resulted in a transition zone location much deeper than that identified from the salinity profile at a borehole drilled on the island near Milrow. A sequential conditioning approach is implemented where the different concentration-related data sets are combined as a single data set and are used to first condition the parameter distribution. Head data are subsequently used as a second conditioning data set where the posterior distribution developed by the first conditioning is used as a prior for this second conditioning. Significant uncertainty reduction is achieved for model input parameters (recharge, R , conductivity, K , and recharge-conductivity ratio, R/K) with the R/K ratio experiencing a very dramatic reduction

1. INTRODUCTION

Three underground nuclear tests were conducted by the United States on Amchitka Island, Alaska in the 1960s and early 1970s. As part of recent environmental management efforts, groundwater modeling has been performed for these sites to improve predictions of contaminant transport behavior.

The groundwater flow and radionuclide transport at the Amchitka Island underground nuclear tests were modeled using two-dimensional numerical simulations as described in Hassan *et al.* (2002). The flow model was conceptualized to address the problem of density-driven flow encountered in the saltwater intrusion environment. A multi-parameter uncertainty analysis was adapted and used to address the effects of the uncertainties associated with the definition of the modeled processes and the values of the parameters governing these

processes. A calibration was performed for each test location using head data and groundwater chemistry data from nearby boreholes as calibration targets. Simultaneous, exact matches of these two independent data sets were not achieved at any site, though the uncertainty expressed by the standard deviation in the base-case flow models encompassed the observed data. Results were presented as expected values and uncertainties of radionuclide mass flux leaving the groundwater system and discharging into the bottom of the ocean.

After the groundwater modeling was complete, additional data collection efforts were conducted on the island. Of most importance to the seawater intrusion groundwater model are magnetotelluric (MT) measurements for determining the subsurface salinity and porosity structure of the Island (Unsworth *et al.*, 2005). Magnetotelluric data were collected on profiles that passed through each of the three test sites. The data presented in Unsworth *et al.* (2005) showed a pattern of increasing, decreasing, and increasing resistivity at each test site on Amchitka. The inflection point of the resistivity profile, where resistivity begins to decrease, is interpreted as the top of the transition zone (TZ) where the salinity increases. The deeper inflection point (increase in resistivity after its decrease with depth) is interpreted as the base of the transition zone, where salinity remains constant and porosity decreases (Unsworth *et al.*, 2005).

This independent set of data provides an opportunity for conditioning the distributions of the model parameters and reducing their uncertainty and that of the model output. To accomplish this, data pertaining to the location of the freshwater lens (from the interpretation of the MT data) are used along with the initial parameter distributions to tighten these distributions around the new data.

Interest in the assessment of parameter uncertainty in hydrologic models and advances in computing technology have led to the use of Monte Carlo-based methods. Among these methods, the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method is a rigorous tool for solving the inverse problem (calibration problem) in a Bayesian framework that benefits from prior knowledge as well as newly collected data.

This paper examines the use of the MCMC method to develop, quantify, and constrain the uncertainty in flow model parameters using all available information for one of the three sites modeled; the Milrow site. The paper is organized as follows. Section 2 presents a brief review of the original groundwater flow model for the Milrow site (Hassan *et al.*, 2001, 2002; Pohlmann *et al.*, 2002). In Section 3, the theoretical background about Bayesian statistical inference and the MCMC approach is presented. Section 4 presents the MCMC analysis for Milrow, focusing on sensitivity studies performed to support choices regarding the application. The results are summarized in Section 5.

2. THE MILROW FLOW MODEL

Amchitka is a long, thin island separating the Bering Sea and Pacific Ocean, predominantly consisting of Tertiary-age submarine and subaerially deposited volcanic rocks. The Milrow test occurred in the lowland plateau region of the island, at a depth of 1,220 m. Data show that hydraulic head decreases with increasing depth through the freshwater lens, supporting the basic conceptualization of freshwater recharge across the island surface with downward-directed gradients to the TZ above seawater. Samples of groundwater from a deep well at Milrow indicated that the test was conducted below the TZ. In addition to chemical

data from wells and boreholes, numerous packer tests were performed and provide hydraulic data, and abundant cores were collected and analyzed for transport properties (such as porosity and sorption).

The conceptual model of flow is governed by the principles of island hydraulics. Recharge of precipitation on the ground surface maintains a freshwater lens by active circulation downward and outward to discharge on the sea floor. Below the TZ there is a very low velocity counter-circulation in the salt-water zone, driven by the loss of salt dispersed into the TZ and recharged by infiltration along the sea floor far beyond the beach margin, past the freshwater discharge zone. A groundwater divide is assumed to exist, coincident with the topographic divide, separating flow to the Bering Sea from flow to the Pacific Ocean.

The boundary conditions for the two-dimensional flow problem entail no flow coinciding with the groundwater divide and along the bottom boundary (Figure 1). The seaward boundary is defined by specified head and constant concentration equivalent to seawater. The top boundary has two segments. The portion across the island receives a recharge flux at a freshwater concentration, and the portion along the ocean is a specified head dependent on the bathymetry. Figure 1 displays the topographic and bathymetric profiles constituting the model's top boundary, the model domain and discretization, and boundary conditions.

FIGURE 1. Milrow topographic and bathymetric profiles that determine the upper boundary of the simulation domain (a), and the discretization and boundary conditions (b).

Island-specific data are used to constrain the parameter values used to construct the seawater intrusion flow problem. Hydraulic conductivity (K) data collected from six boreholes are used to calculate the best estimate for a homogeneous conductivity value and the range of uncertainty associated with this estimate. The geologic environment suggests strong anisotropy, so that vertical hydraulic conductivity, K_{zz} , is assumed to be one-tenth the horizontal value (except in the chimney above the nuclear cavity, where collapse is assumed

to increase K_{zz} relative to that of the horizontal conductivity, K_{xx}). The cavity and chimney location is shown by the bold elements in Figure 1b. Temperature logs measured in several boreholes and water balance estimates are used to derive groundwater recharge (R) values.

The model was calibrated using site-specific hydraulic head and water chemistry data. The objective of the calibration was to select base-case, uniform flow, and saltwater intrusion parameters that yield a modeling result as close as possible to that observed in the natural system. Difficulty was encountered in obtaining simultaneous best fit to the two targets (head and chemistry). The critical calibration feature for locating the mid-point of the TZ is the ratio of recharge to hydraulic conductivity (R/K). Compromises were made to achieve the optimum fit to both heads and chemistry, and more weight was given to the hydraulic head measurements due to reported difficulties encountered in obtaining representative water samples from these very deep boreholes during drilling operations.

Based on the results of a parametric uncertainty analysis, multiple realizations of the flow field, with varying K , R , and porosity (n), were generated to evaluate the effect of uncertainty in these parameters on the flow and transport results. Three random distributions were generated for K , R , and n . Head and chloride concentration data were used as criteria to ensure that the combined random distributions led to realistic flow solutions.

3. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND

The Markov Chain Monte Carlo method is used to simulate the posterior distribution that relies on prior knowledge and new information. MCMC is a multidimensional random sampling procedure where the parameter value of the next sample only depends on the parameter value of the current sampling point. In MCMC, the posterior distributions of model parameters are generated by drawing several thousands of samples from the posterior distributions, and calculating their empirical mean, standard deviation, and percentiles. In this, it is similar to simple Monte Carlo simulation, except that Monte Carlo draws samples from what is, in effect, a prior distribution, and does not update this with likelihood.

While many different MCMC sampling algorithms exist, the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm is the most common (Marshall *et al.*, 2004). The Metropolis-Hastings algorithm produces a Markov chain sequence of samples that constitute a random walk in the parameter space. Each iteration of the algorithm generates proposed (or candidate) parameter samples using a suitable arbitrary probability distribution referred to as the proposal density or the jump distribution. These proposed values are either accepted or rejected using a criterion, which ensures the algorithm is sampling from the posterior distribution when the Markov chain has become stationary.

The application of the Metropolis-Hastings algorithm for drawing samples from the posterior distribution can be summarized as follows (Marshall *et al.*, 2004):

- 1) Start the simulation at iteration $i = 0$ with an arbitrary chosen initial parameter vector $\Theta = \Theta^0$.
- 2) Generate a proposed value Θ^* for Θ from a proposal density depending on the current value Θ^i of Θ .
- 3) Compute an acceptance probability α (depending on Θ^i , Θ^* , the proposal density, and the model) that determines whether the proposed value Θ^* is accepted or not.
- 4) Accept $\Theta^{i+1} = \Theta^*$ with probability α . Otherwise $\Theta^{i+1} = \Theta^i$.

5) Increment iteration i and repeat steps 2-4.

The difficult step of evaluating the moments and other statistics of the posterior distribution in Bayesian inference is circumvented in this algorithm as one can get a reliable estimate of these moments once a large sample of parameter values has been generated. This assumes that the sample moments converge to the moments of the distribution, and that for a given starting value Θ^0 and a given proposal density, the parameter sequence Θ^i has converged in distribution to the stationary posterior distribution (Smith and Roberts, 1993; Campbell *et al.*, 1999). This can be achieved by discarding the first few thousand “burn in” simulations or samples that are influenced by the initial value.

4. MCMC ANALYSIS

The MCMC method is applied to develop posterior distributions conditioned on prior knowledge and available data, including the original salinity and head data and new data gathered by Unsworth *et al.* (2005). The salinity data consisted of ten data points and the head data included 5 data points. The MT data provided a profile along a large portion of the domain that could be subjectively converted to salinity data providing as many as 500 points for the model elements. There are many ways to combine the three data sets and use them in the MCMC conditioning. Both the water salinity measurements and the MT-interpreted salinity provide information on the same system parameter, though the abundance of MT-derived data overwhelms the water chemistry data. A sequential conditioning approach is applied. The combined salinity-MT data set is used for conditioning and developing posterior distributions for the model parameters. These posterior distributions are then used as the prior distributions for conditioning on the hydraulic head data, leading to a final set of posterior distributions.

Figure 2 exhibits the MCMC conditioning results for Milrow. In the figure, $P(R)$, $P(K)$, and $P(R/K)$ denote the prior distributions taken as the distributions used in the 2002 model. $P(R | D_1)$, $P(K | D_1)$, and $P(R/K | D_1)$ denote the first posterior obtained after conditioning on the combined salinity and MT-converted concentrations. Lastly, $P(R | D_2)$, $P(K | D_2)$, and $P(R/K | D_2)$ denote the final posterior distributions obtained using $P(R | D_1)$, $P(K | D_1)$, and $P(R/K | D_1)$ as the prior distributions when conditioning on the head data.

The recharge prior and posterior distributions are plotted in Figure 2a. After the first conditioning on the combined concentration data set (MT-converted concentrations and the chloride concentrations from UAe-2) the resulting posterior (dashed line) is shifted toward higher recharge values with less spread than the prior (solid line). The range of recharge values is slightly reduced from 0.2 to 6 cm/yr to 0.5 to 6 cm/yr. The peak of the distribution has remained the same but its location has moved from a recharge value of about 1.2 cm/yr to 1.95 cm/yr (i.e., the distribution mode has changed). Subsequent conditioning on the heads yields a noticeable increase in the peak of the density function (compare dashed and dotted curves) and as a result, a significant decrease in the spread (σ_R decreased from 1.107 to 0.703 after head conditioning).

Conditioning on the combined concentration data yields a much narrower distribution for K than its prior (Figure 2b). The range of possible conductivity values is reduced from [0.002 to 0.05 m/d] to [0.002 to 0.03 m/d]. The peak of the distribution is slightly shifted toward a lower conductivity value (i.e., the mode of the distribution has decreased) but with a higher density than the prior distribution. So in effect, the tails of the prior distribution are trimmed

after the first conditioning on the combined concentration data set and the peak of the density function is increased. When conditioning is performed sequentially on the head data, a slight shift toward higher conductivity values occurs as can be seen in comparing $P(K | D_1)$ to $P(K | D_2)$. The peak also increased and σ_K decreased from 5.5×10^{-3} to 4.1×10^{-3} m/d.

FIGURE 2. Results of the sequential conditioning approach for Milrow, where D_1 is the combined salinity data set and D_2 is the head data at UAe-2.

The impact of conditioning through MCMC is greatest for R/K as shown in Figure 2c. Conditioning on the combined concentration data greatly reduces the density spreading and increases the peak density value more than twofold. In addition, the conditioning shifts the distribution toward higher R/K values with the peak density occurring at a value of 200 compared to a value of about 79 in the prior distribution. This makes sense, as the data set is mainly controlled by the MT-converted concentrations. The MT data indicate a deeper transition zone than that indicated by the salinity data, which qualitatively guided the prior selection in the 2002 model. The range of possible values for this ratio is tightened, where it was [5 to 400] in the prior distribution and [120 to 300] in the posterior. When the head data are used in a sequential manner to condition the distribution, the final R/K posterior (dotted curve) is shifted toward lower ratios and the peak density increases.

Conditioning on salinity and MT data yields large R/K values and a deeper transition zone than indicated by the heads. When we subsequently condition on heads, the transition zone moves up and becomes shallower to honor the head data and R/K gets a little smaller (moving R/K posterior to the left). Considering the three data sets individually, the salinity data require lower R/K values (shallow transition zone) than heads, and heads require lower values than MT data. So when the MT-converted data set is used along with the salinity data, the R/K distribution is pushed to the highest values because of the dominance of the MT data, but

when, subsequently, the attempt is made to accommodate heads, they pull the R/K posterior back to a location that gives a slightly shallower transition zone.

Note that the posterior distributions plotted in Figure 2a and b are the marginal posterior distributions for R and K , respectively. It is clear that despite being a small data set, the heads have a noticeable effect on the marginal posterior distributions of R and K , and a more pronounced effect on the posterior distribution of R/K . Also, the posterior distributions are closer to being normal, especially for R/K .

The above results are based on the theoretical prior and posterior fitted to the original 300 realizations and the MCMC-generated 90,000 values (100,000 iterations minus the 10,000 burn-in iterations), respectively. Comparing the actual values of R and K (Figure 3) shows that the posterior pairs have a very strong positive correlation, which was not present in the prior pairs. The range of R/K is very tight around the 170 value (Figure 3b), whereas in the prior, the range had a long tail toward the higher values of R/K (Figure 3a).

FIGURE 3. Recharge-conductivity pairs (a) as used in the Milrow 2002 model, and (b) generated from the MCMC algorithm.

5.0 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

The combined concentration data set (water salinity and MT interpretations) yields a posterior recharge distribution with higher recharge values than the prior, and as such, the mean of the posterior is higher than the prior mean. The spreading of the distribution (i.e., σ_R) decreases after conditioning on the combined data set, reflecting a reduction in uncertainty. The combined concentration data also impact the hydraulic conductivity distribution, not significantly in terms of shifting the mean, but rather by significantly trimming the tails of the prior distribution. For R/K , the first conditioning yields dramatic effects, shifting the distribution toward higher R/K values and dramatically decreasing spreading (about 70

percent reduction in $\sigma_{R/K}$). The shift toward higher ratios causes an increase in the distribution mean of about 39 percent

The impact of heads through the second conditioning (using the first posterior as a prior) is smaller than that of the combined concentration data, mainly due to the limited number of head measurements relative to the combined concentration data set. The heads shift the recharge distribution toward lower values. This shift is accompanied by a reduction in spreading, compared to first posterior. Conditioning on heads also led to a shift toward higher hydraulic conductivities.

The conditioning impact on the ratio R/K is more significant than on the individual parameters. The final R/K posterior shifts toward lower values of R/K than found in the first posterior. Compared to the prior, the final posterior leads to higher ratios, and significant uncertainty reduction (reduced $\sigma_{R/K}$) results from the MCMC conditioning on the different data sets. Table 1 summarizes these results.

TABLE 1. Summary of MCMC results showing percent reduction in variance.

Conditioning on	% Reduction in Variance (Prior σ^2 -Posterior σ^2)/Prior σ^2			% Reduction in Variance (Prior σ^2 -Final Posterior σ^2)/Prior σ^2		
	R	K	R/K	R	K	R/K
D_1 (Combined salinity data and MT-converted concentration)	35.56	72.03	91.37	74.01	96.15	94.44
D_2 (Head data)	59.67	44.43	35.58			

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